

E-LaaS

Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

CONFERENCE PANEL

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

TRANSPORT of the 21stCENTURY

Dedicated project panel – selected research highlights

SUB-REPORT FOR WP6

Authors: Emilian Szczepański, Konrad Lewczuk, Marianna Jacyna (Warsaw University of Technology)

Date: 31.10.2025

Project implemented as part of the call ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC China Call) organized by JPI Urban Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 875022.

European
Commission

Project funding information

E-Laas project is carried out in an international consortium. Project coordinator in Europe: Chalmers University of Technology (Sweden), project coordinator in China: Shanghai University (China), consortium members: Tsinghua University (China), Warsaw University of Technology (Poland), cooperation partners: Stockholms stad, Trafikkontoret (Sweden), ParkUnload (Spain), Metropolis GZM (Poland), Shanghai Urban-Rural Construction and Transportation Department (China), Volvo Group Trucks Technology and Operations (Sweden).

- *The Chinese part of the project is funded by National Natural Science Foundation of China*

- *The Swedish part of the project is funded by Swedish Energy Agency*

- *The Polish part of the project is funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (project no. 2022/04/Y/ST8/00134). The value of the co-financing is PLN 878,107.00. Project duration 27/04/2023 - 26/04/2026 (36 months).*

I. Aims of the panel

From September 2 to 5, 2025, the Transport XXI Conference took place in Ryn, Poland. This well-established scientific event, widely recognized among both academics and practitioners in the field of transport and logistics, included a dedicated thematic panel focusing on the research project E-Laas (Energy Optimal Urban Logistics as a Service).

The main objective of the panel was to summarize the research findings obtained so far and to discuss selected aspects related to energy optimization in urban logistics systems. The session aimed to facilitate knowledge exchange among participants and to collect feedback from the academic community and industry representatives regarding the feasibility of implementing the proposed solutions. Furthermore, it sought to identify potential directions for further research within the project framework. The panel served as a platform to present the project's key achievements and as an inspiration for the continued development of innovative and sustainable models for urban logistics.

The E-Laas panel was held on September 5, 2025, from 8:30 to 10:00 a.m. The session was attended by approximately 20 participants on-site and one remote speaker. A total of four presentations in English were delivered, covering various aspects of the project.

In addition, during the plenary session on September 5, a presentation in Polish was delivered by Michał Kłodawski and Konrad Lewczuk, entitled “*Simulation Analysis of Energy Consumption in Last-Mile Deliveries*”, which presented selected findings from the E-Laas project.

II. E-Laas panel agenda

1. Ze Zhou, Fangting Zhou, Balázs Adam Kulcsár: *Last-mile delivery problem with flexible time and location options under stochastic customer behaviour*
2. Jakub Murawski, Piotr Franke: *Sustainable logistics in polish cities – an overview of transport policies*
3. Konrad Lewczuk, Michał Kłodawski: *Multi-domain microsimulation for evaluating energy efficiency in last-mile distribution*
4. Emilian Szczepański, Jan Paszkowski: *Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system*
5. Discussion

III. Discussion and key conclusions

During the discussion following the presentations, participants addressed issues related to the rationale for developing separate Sustainable Urban Logistics Plans (SULPs) as opposed to integrating them as components of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMPs). An important part of the debate also concerned the quality and availability of data necessary for modelling freight transport systems at both micro and macro levels.

The main conclusions drawn from the panel and subsequent discussion were as follows:

- It is essential to develop and implement Sustainable Urban Logistics Plans in accordance with established methodological frameworks, while simultaneously applying standardized indicators that allow for the comparison of the effectiveness of implemented solutions.
- Enhanced cooperation among logistics operators in the field of data sharing is required, as it can significantly improve the quality of analyses and simulations.
- There is a need to improve the quality of transport models developed on behalf of cities and local authorities so that they better reflect the complexity of urban logistics processes.
- Advanced optimization models that consider the impact of consumer decision-making on last-mile delivery processes, including their energy demand implications, provide valuable insights for logistics operators in shaping their operational strategies.
- Participants emphasized that future research should increasingly take into account the social responsibility dimension of logistics, as well as the integration of logistics systems with urban energy infrastructure.

IV. Attachments

- 1) Presentations (E-Laas Panel – polish team presentations)
- 2) Conference programme first pages, and page for conference panel

Attachment 1:

Presentation II.2

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Sustainable logistics in polish cities – an overview of transport policies

Jakub Murawski, Piotr Franke-Wąsowski

Warsaw University of Technology
Faculty of Transport

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Challenges and expectations

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

City logistics policies

National level, for example:

- Transport Development Strategy 2030
- National Regional Development Strategy 2030

Regional level

- SUMPs
- SULPs

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan

- a strategic plan aimed at ensuring sustainable mobility development in a selected metropolitan area
- the SUMP integrates various urban policies: transport, environmental, spatial, and economic.
- the implementation of policies described in the SUMP should lead to:
 - increased transport accessibility for inhabitants, businesses, and institutions,
 - reduced congestion,
 - lower environmental impact,
 - development of sustainable forms of mobility – public transport, cycling, walking, and micromobility.

SUMP vs SULP

Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan:

- planning the development of mobility in metropolitan areas
- covers the entire transport system – pedestrian, cycling, motor vehicle, micromobility, and public transport
- target groups: residents, passengers, local authorities, public transport operators, and carriers

Sustainable Urban Logistics Plan:

- shaping the flow of goods and organizing deliveries
- focuses exclusively on transport modes used for freight distribution
- target groups: residents, local authorities, entrepreneurs, logistics operators, and carriers

Research Method

- Review of SUMP documents implemented in 46 Functional Urban Areas in Poland (as of August 29, 2025).
- The area where the analyzed SUMP are being implemented has a population of over 22 million people.
- Analysis of documents in terms of policies regarding freight transport, urban logistics, and last-mile delivery.
- Categorization of identified solutions and good practices.

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

City logistics policies in Poland

Three groups of regions:

- detailed logistics policy measures included in the SUMP
- general logistics policy measures included in the SUMP (for example, emphasizing the need to develop SULP)
- city logistics not addressed in the SUMP

Created with Datawrapper

Goals identified in SUMP

Reducing the negative impact of deliveries on inhabitants, including:

- improving air quality,
- reducing noise,
- enhancing spatial order,
- decreasing traffic intensity,
- increasing the number of available parking spaces.

City logistics policy measures in Poland

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Truck traffic restrictions

- Most common policy measure in Polish regions
- Different approaches. In some cities, restrictions apply only to transit traffic, while in others, a complete ban on heavy goods vehicle (HGV) entry into the inner city is being considered.
- Selective restrictions affecting only specific vehicle types (e.g., GVW over 3.5 tonnes) or applying during selected hours, days, or on specific road sections.
- Infrastructure prerequisite. Effective restrictions may require the construction of new road infrastructure (e.g., ring roads), which necessitates close cooperation with road authorities (e.g., GDDKiA).
- Logistics support measures. Truck-entry restrictions may require the development of urban micro-hubs to ensure efficient last-mile deliveries within restricted areas.

Delivery vehicle parking spaces

- Two approaches:
 - Designating permanent or time-limited parking spaces (e.g., during specific hours) exclusively for first-/last-mile deliveries.
 - Defining delivery parking zones where goods deliveries are permitted.
- The success of implementation depends, among other factors, on effective enforcement to ensure proper use of designated delivery spaces, thereby preventing passenger cars from occupying them.
- It is possible to integrate this approach with an ITS system that provides real-time information about available parking spaces dedicated to deliveries.
- Example (Zielona Góra):
Designating parking spots exclusively for delivery vehicles (sign 'no parking' with the annotation 'except for deliveries up to 15 minutes'), in coordination with the owners of nearby commercial and service establishments. One parking space should be allocated for every 4–5 premises requiring supplies to ensure proper rotation.

„Soft” policy measures

- Various types of soft policy measures, such as developing concepts, initiating dialogue with businesses, or creating working groups.
- *Examples:*
 - *Cooperation with delivery companies and their contractors to establish delivery rules (Gorzów Wielkopolski)*
 - *Developing a concept for the logistics service of the inner city centre using forms of sustainable urban mobility (Kraków, Koszalin-Kołobrzeg)*
 - *Collaboration and dialogue on route planning between infrastructure managers to explore possibilities for reducing the impact on road infrastructure (Rybnik)*
 - *Detailed studies of delivery traffic combined with stakeholder consultations (Gdańsk-Sopot-Gdynia)*
 - *Lobbying and supporting the location of logistics centres to enable deliveries with smaller vehicles (Łuków, Zamość)*
 - *Cooperation with carriers regarding e-commerce deliveries (Puławy)*

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Micro-hubs

- Logistics micro-hubs are small transshipment facilities located close to areas with high delivery demand, usually in central urban zones.
- They enable a reduction in the use of large freight vehicles and promote the increased deployment of zero-emission transport modes (e.g., cargo bikes, electric scooters, light electric vehicles).
- Shared infrastructure – micro-hubs can be integrated into cooperative platforms serving multiple logistics operators, which helps reduce operational costs.
- Coordination of multiple stakeholders is required – effective implementation demands cooperation with local authorities, logistics operators, carriers, and property owners.
- Example (Wrocław):
Recommendations were provided for the location of logistics and courier centres, including identifying potential locations that could negatively impact residential areas, for instance, due to increased traffic loads.

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Cargo bikes

- Establishing an incentive system for logistics operators and carriers to promote the use of cargo bikes in first- and last-mile delivery by granting cargo bikes priority access to selected urban areas (e.g., historic city centres).
- It typically involves the designation of specific locations where transshipment from delivery vehicles to cargo bikes can take place (e.g., micro-hubs).
- The implementation also requires the development of infrastructure that facilitates cargo bike movement.
- As part of the incentive framework, it is also recommended to establish dedicated parking spaces for cargo bikes to support efficient operations.
- Example (Gorzów Wielkopolski):
Support for the development of deliveries using cargo bikes through the adaptation of urban infrastructure and the integration of cargo bikes into the public bike-sharing system.

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Rail freight facilities

- Creating an incentive system to increase the use of rail transport in city logistics
- In many cities, there are unused railway lines and sidings that can be reintegrated into logistics operations, enabling the efficient delivery of goods to urban areas.
- Where the existing infrastructure is insufficient, it is possible to build new short railway sections and dedicated transshipment terminals supporting deliveries via rail transport (e.g., micro-hubs).
- Successful implementation requires infrastructure investments and coordination among multiple stakeholders, including railway network managers, logistics operators, rail carriers, and local authorities.
- Example (Koszalin–Kołobrzeg):
Development of logistics centres near existing railway sidings and modernisation of rail infrastructure, including sidings and transshipment ramps.

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Parcel lockers

- Incorrect location of parcel lockers may:
 - generate additional traffic in areas where it is not acceptable,
 - force delivery vehicles to enter sections restricted to traffic (e.g., parks),
 - disrupt spatial order, negatively affecting the functionality of public spaces,
- Require dialogue with logistics operators regarding suitable locations for parcel lockers and the organization of deliveries,
- Involve the development of location guidelines for parcel lockers to ensure they do not negatively impact residents,
- Necessitate pedestrian accessibility analyses and consideration of the proximity of other pickup points to minimize unnecessary delivery-related traffic.

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Summary (1/2)

- The dynamic growth of e-commerce leads to a significant increase in delivery traffic within cities, resulting in challenges related to congestion, air quality, noise, and spatial order.
- The analysis of 46 SUMP documents in Poland shows that urban logistics aspects are addressed at varying levels. There is a growing need to integrate mobility and logistics policies and to develop SULPs as complementary planning documents.
- In Polish metropolitan areas, the most frequently formulated city logistics policy measures include:
 - truck traffic restrictions,
 - the designation of dedicated parking spaces for delivery vehicles.

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Summary (2/2)

- Many urban logistics policy measures are closely interrelated. For example, the development of micro-hubs can be combined with restrictions on truck access to city centres and the increased use of cargo bikes for last-mile deliveries, creating a complementary and efficient logistics ecosystem.
- Successful implementation requires close cooperation among local authorities, logistics operators, carriers, and residents, as well as investments in infrastructure supporting sustainable urban logistics.

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Thank you for your attention

This research was funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (project no. 2022/04/Y/ST8/00134).

Project title: Energy optimal urban logistics as a service (E-Laas).

Project implemented as part of the call ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (EN-UAC China Call) organized by JPI Urban Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC) funded from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 875022.

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

19

Presentation II.3

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Multi-domain microsimulation for evaluating energy efficiency in last last-mile distribution

Wieloobszarowa mikrosymulacja do badania efektywności energetycznej systemów dystrybucyjnych ostatniej mili

Konrad Lewczuk, Michał Kłodawski

Project

E-Laas: Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

The problems of urban logistics

Urban development goals	Domains of activity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Law legal compliance • Resident comfort and health • Budget efficiency 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Distribution & freight transport 2. Public transport 3. Municipal services 4. Waste management 5. Infrastructure development 6. Control systems (ITS) 7. Entry and access policy 8. Taxes, licenses, and permits
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate goals (if not included in legal acts) • Crisis-era operational safety 	

Last-mile services as one of the **critical logistics processes** in the city

- **Problems:** interaction of modes, routing (VRPs), location, scheduling, resources assignment, behaviour modelling, safety
- Motivation for **simulation-based optimization**

European Commission

URBAN EUROPE

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

MDIFMS (*multi-domain integration framework for microsimulation*)

- Interconnected domains: transportation networks, energy systems, urban infrastructure, stakeholder behaviour
- ABM – stakeholder interactions and distributed decision-making
- DES – dynamics and system state
- Assumptions: Spatial, Temporal, Suprastructure, Energy, Demand, Network & infrastructure, Environmental, Data, Performance, Stochastic, Validation, Toolbox

Spatial assumptions

- **Regions** (uniform customer distribution)
- Topology with **location** of depots, customers and intermediate facilities
- Linked **modal** networks (transition points)

Temporal assumptions

- Hourly **time steps** for energy demand and supply modelling
- Daily **operational cycles** (peak and off-peak periods)
- **Seasonal** variations in energy consumption

Suprastructure assumptions

- Heterogeneous fleet (all types of vehicles for LMD)
- Vehicle **energy consumption** parameters
- Energy consumption **variability** patterns
- **Capacity** limits
- Driver **working time** restrictions
- Vehicle **availability** windows
- **Service** time variations (stochastic components)

Energy system assumptions

- **Tractive** energy
- **Auxiliary** energy (heating, cooling, onboard systems)
- Energy **losses** in transmission
- **Grid** electricity (time-varying carbon intensity, pricing)
- **Renewable** energy integration
- **Charging** infrastructure capacity and accessibility for EV

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

MDIFMS (*multi-domain integration framework for microsimulation*)

- Interconnected domains: transportation networks, energy systems, urban infrastructure, stakeholder behaviour
- ABM – stakeholder interactions and distributed decision-making
- DES – dynamics and system state
- Assumptions: Spatial, Temporal, Suprastructure, Energy, Demand, Network & infrastructure, Environmental, Data, Performance, Stochastic, Validation, Toolbox

Demand assumptions

- Demand under spatial / temporal patterns (**stochastic variations**)
- Package size and weight distributions (**historical data**)
- **Time window** preferences
- Choice behaviour for delivery options (**multinomial logistic regression**)
- **Trip chaning** behaviour for customers
- Walking **distance** thresholds

Network and infrastructure assumptions

- Congestion-dependent **travel times**
- Traffic signal timing and **coordination**
- Urban **constraints** (loading zones, access restrictions, parking)
- **Warehouse** and distribution centre locations and capacities
- **Energy** consumption for warehousing
- LM **facilities** (energy requirements)
- Land **pricing**, taxes and rents
- **Collaboration** patterns
- PPPs

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

MDIFMS (*multi-domain integration framework for microsimulation*)

- Interconnected domains: transportation networks, energy systems, urban infrastructure, stakeholder behaviour
- ABM – stakeholder interactions and distributed decision-making
- DES – dynamics and system state
- Assumptions: Spatial, Temporal, Suprastructure, Energy, Demand, Network & infrastructure, Environmental, Data, Performance, Stochastic, Validation, Toolbox

Environmental assumptions

- Weather and seasons
- Temperature effects on energy consumption
- Wind and precipitation impacts
- Seasonal variations in energy demand / supply patterns
- Regulatory and logistics policies
- Emission standards and access zones
- Energy pricing and tariffs

Data assumptions

- Real-time traffic
- Energy consumption data from vehicles
- Historical delivery patterns and customer behaviour
- Building energy consumption data
- Weather and environmental monitoring

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

MDIFMS (multi-domain integration framework for microsimulation)

- Interconnected domains: transportation networks, energy systems, urban infrastructure, stakeholder behaviour
- ABM – stakeholder interactions and distributed decision-making
- DES – dynamics and system state
- Assumptions: Spatial, Temporal, Suprastructure, Energy, Demand, Network & infrastructure, Environmental, Data, Performance, Stochastic, Validation, Toolbox

Performance metrics

- Energy efficiency
- Total energy consumption per package, tkm
- Peak load reduction and demand response
- GHG emissions
- Operational performance
- Delivery success rates
- Customer satisfaction
- Vehicle utilization
- System throughput

Toolbox

- Metaheuristics: GA, PSO, ACO, A*, GH, hybrid approaches
- Dynamic optimization: ADP, RL (ML)

Stochastics

- Customer demand variations (seasonal, daily)
- DCs operation
- Customer availability
- System reliability (vehicle breakdown and maintenance)
- Infrastructure reliability
- Communication reliability

Validation / calibration assumptions

- Historical operation data
- Energy consumption measurements from actual vehicles
- Customer survey
- Sensitivity analysis for key parameter variations

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Microsimulation in last mile services: use-cases

Case study #1:

- Stakeholder collaboration model in parcel locker networks
- Business clusters in defined urban areas
- Shared use of parcel locker infrastructure
- Access models: co-ownership or subscription to 3rd-party lockers
- Locker locations determined by MCDM (demand density, walkability, transport nodes).
- Optional: shared fleets & micro-hubs for last-mile transshipment.
- Optional: regulatory impact considered (e.g., zoning, emissions policies).

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Microsimulation in last mile services: use-cases

Case study #2:

- Multi-modal last-mile service involving couriers, parcel lockers, drones, and recipients' own transport
- Comparative analysis of energy consumption and process efficiency across different organizational scenarios
- Customer surveys used as input for algorithm-driven decision-making
- Implementation of various routing heuristics for network searching
- Input for macroscale simulation

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Microsimulation in last mile services: use-cases

Case study #3:

- CVRP with battery charging (EVCVRP)
- Variable locations of charging stations and service depots
- Diverse battery and charging technologies considered
- Heuristic approaches: a) order of input, b) sequential node attachment, c) nearest neighbour
- Open datasets for delivery and pickup scenarios
- Resistance functions applied to road segments
- GIS-based network used for routing analysis

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Conclusions and Implications

Gains:

- Incorporation of **local conditions** into last-mile service planning (survey data, environmental analysis)
- **Scenario analyses** of heuristic and optimal decision-making **algorithms** for location planning, routing, and service option selection
- **Evaluation of the efficiency**, energy consumption, cost, and user comfort associated with last-mile services
- Comparative analysis of **baseline vs. optimized models**
- Key insights for decision-makers in logistics design and input for macrosimulation

Challenges:

- Microsimulation is limited to **local-scale problems** by the high level of model detail and computational resource demands
- Need to conduct a **series of detailed analyses** tailored to various decision-making challenges
- **Difficulty in representing social behaviour** and user expectations, particularly with regard to emerging last-mile technologies.

E-Laas Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service | European Commission | URBAN EUROPE | NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Multi-domain microsimulation for evaluating energy efficiency in last last-mile distribution

Thank you!

Project: E-Laas: Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service
This research was funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (project no. 2022/04/Y/ST8/00134). Project title: Energy optimal urban logistics as a service (E-Laas). Project implemented as part of the call ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (EN-UAC China Call) organized by JPI Urban Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC) funded from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 875022.

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - 2025

Presentation II.4

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Wydział Transportu

Politechnika Warszawska

Faculty of Transport

Warsaw University of Technology

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

Jan Paszkowski, Emilian Szczepański

Warsaw University of Technology
Faculty of Transport

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

1

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Agenda

1. Introduction
2. Macrosimulation in PTV Visum
3. Emission models
4. Data input
5. Data output
6. Analysis area
7. Base energy and emission results
8. Scenarios description
9. Scenarios results
10. Conclusions and further research

2

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
Energy optimal urban
Logistics As A Service

European
Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE
CENTRUM
NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

2

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Introduction

- Macroscopic models deliver a complex set of traffic data within the analysis area
- Road network and transportation policy development scenarios in macroscopic modeling can facilitate a decision process by indicating the optimal solution in terms of traffic or time loss reduction
- Emission modeling tools using macroscopic model traffic data can enhance the impact forecast by adding the emission analysis
- Urban logistics optimisation is often not considered enough in cities' traffic policies
- Energy consumption and emission reduction is important factor in urban transport and logistics planning
- Urban logistics environmental factors are often oversaw in the transport planning
- It still lacks a proper research of the emission analysis accountability using the macroscopic modeling data

3

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
Energy optimal urban
Logistics As A Service

European
Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE
CENTRUM
NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

3

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Macrosimulation in PTV Visum

Supply and demand

- Supply – transport network
 - Nodes: place of the links intersection
 - Links: connects nodes and traffic
- Demand: Desire to travel:
 - Trips generated by researching the travel needs of the population
 - Each trip set between origin and destination

Four step model

- Trip generation: desire to travel in zone
- Origin-destination matrix: Trips between zones
- Modal split: Origin-destination matrices for each mode of transport (car, public transport, freight)
- Traffic assignment: Assigning each trip to the optimal the set of links between origin and destination

4

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

European Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Emission models

- Both models estimate traffic-related emissions (e.g., CO₂, NO_x, PM) and Energy consumption (MJ)
- Integrated into PTVVisum macroscopic software for assessing environmental impacts of transport scenarios

Aspect	COPERT	HBEFA
Developer / Source	European Environment Agency (EEA)	European Agencies (Germany, Switzerland, Austria, etc.)
Main Application	National & Regional Emission Inventories	Urban & regional traffic studies
Spatial Scale	Macro-scale (large areas)	Micro to meso-scale (urban areas, corridors)
Input Detail	Fleet averages, average speed	Detailed by vehicle type, Euro class, driving situation
Emission Factor Basis	Average speed functions	Driving situation-specific
Best Use Cases	Strategic & long-term policy analysis	Urban traffic planning & environmental impact assessment

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

European Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Data input and calculation

- In PTV Visum, enable procedure COPERT or HBEFA emission calculation
 - Assign the vehicle compositions (or create own) from the HBEFA or COPERT database to the transport modes defined in Visum
 - Define which parameters needs to be calculated (emission, cold start emission, energy consumption for defined transport mode)
 - Each link obtains calculated parameters of choice
- Data used for emission calculation:
 - Traffic volumes per link or OD matrix (cars, trucks, buses, etc.)
 - Link lengths (distance of each network segment)
 - Speeds per link (calculated in assignment or given as capacity/speed functions)
 - Traffic situation (level of service from free flow to congested, especially for HBEFA)
 - Vehicle data (vehicle type, fuel type, emission standards)
 - Additional data: (cold start share, road gradients, traffic signalisation)
- In this presentation, COPERT results are presented

6

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

European Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Data output – Energy consumption

- Energy consumptions calculated are:
 - Gasoline consumption [g]
 - Diesel consumption [g]
 - Energy consumption of electric vehicles [MJ]
- In this research, consumptions are summed up to present a total energy consumption [MJ] for the whole fuel types using the following energy production data of the fuels:
 - Gasoline energy production: 46,7 MJ/kg
 - Diesel energy production: 43,1 MJ/kg

7

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
Energy optimal urban
Logistics As A Service

European Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Data output – Emission calculation

- Emission values units are gram[g]:
 - CO2 carbon dioxide
 - CH4 methane
 - N2O nitrous oxide
 - PM particle matters up to 10µm
 - PM non-exhaust particle matters up to 10µm, non-exhaust
 - PM2.5 particle matters up to 2.5µm
 - PM2.5 non-exhaust particle matters up to 2.5µm, non-exhaust
 - BC exhaust black carbon, exhaust
 - BC non-exhaust Black carbon, non-exhaust
 - Pb lead
 - NH3 ammoniac
 - SO2 sulphur dioxide
 - NO2 nitrogen dioxide
 - HC hydrocarbons
 - NMHC Non-methane hydrocarbons
 - Benzene
 - NOx nitrogen oxide
 - CO carbon monoxide
- Emission cost have been calculated according to Handbook on External Costs of Transport prepared by European Commission. Cost [euro per tonne]:
- NOx: 3900 euro/t
 - SO2: 5600 euro/t
 - PM2.5 174500 euro/t

8

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
Energy optimal urban
Logistics As A Service

European Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Analysis area

GZM metropolis, Poland

Vehicle kilometers on the transport network

Level of service

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
Energy optimal urban
Logistics As A Service

European Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

9

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Base energy and emission results

10

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
 Energy optimal urban
 Logistics As A Service

European Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

10

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Energy and emission results – road classes and LoS

11

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
 Energy optimal urban
 Logistics As A Service

European Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

11

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Energy and emission results – dominating zone function

12

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
 Energy optimal urban
 Logistics As A Service

European Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

12

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Scenarios description

1. V1: Zero emission freight traffic: composition of vehicles associated with freight traffic (light and heavy good vehicles) are set as zero emission
2. V2: Peak freight traffic: Seasonal peak of freight traffic operations: 120% of average in-model traffic, according to data in literature

13

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
Energy optimal urban
Logistics As A Service

European
Commission

URBAN EUROPE

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

13

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Scenarios results – total energy consumption reduction V1

14

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
Energy optimal urban
Logistics As A Service

European
Commission

URBAN EUROPE

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

14

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Scenarios results – total emission cost reduction V1

15

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
Energy optimal urban
Logistics As A Service

European
Commission

URBAN EUROPE

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

15

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Scenarios results – total energy consumption increase V2

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
 Energy optimal urban
 Logistics As A Service

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Scenarios results – total emission cost increase V2

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
 Energy optimal urban
 Logistics As A Service

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Scenarios results changes by dominating motivation

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
 Energy optimal urban
 Logistics As A Service

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

Conclusions and further research

- Conclusions:
 - Zones with 'other' and 'logistics centers' motivations are the most sensitive to changes in total energy consumption.
 - Zones with 'retail' and 'warehouses' show the highest sensitivity in freight vehicle energy consumption.
 - Zones with 'industry' and 'logistics centers' are not very sensitive to the freight energy consumption and freight emission because of the more fluent traffic
 - Total emissions are most affected in zones with logistics centers (due to a high share of freight vehicles) and retail.
 - Freight vehicle emissions are most sensitive in zones with 'other' motivation, followed by warehouses.
 - High-class roads are most sensitive to changes in total energy consumption and emissions.
 - Low-class roads are most sensitive to changes in freight vehicle energy consumption and emissions.
- Further research:
 - Emission results validation using the microscopic data or emission sensor data
 - HBEFA and COPERT results comparison
 - More detailed scenarios considering introducing sustainable freight transport solutions

19

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

E-Laas
Energy optimal urban
Logistics As A Service

European
Commission

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE
CENTRUM
NAUKI

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

19

TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU

URBAN EUROPE

Thank you for your attention

Project: E-Laas: Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

This research was funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (project no. 2022/04/Y/ST8/00134). Project title: Energy optimal urban logistics as a service (E-Laas). Project implemented as part of the call ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (EN-UAC China Call) organized by JPI Urban Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC) funded from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 875022.

URBAN EUROPE

NARODOWE
CENTRUM
NAUKI

European
Commission

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowa - Transport of the 21st Century – September 2-5, Ryn, Poland

20

**Attachment 2:
Conference programme**

**WARSAW UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
FACULTY OF TRANSPORT**

**INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE
TRANSPORT
of the 21st CENTURY**

**MIĘDZYNARODOWA KONFERENCJA NAUKOWA
TRANSPORT XXI WIEKU**

PROGRAMME

Program

**Faculty
of Transport**

WARSAW UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

September 2nd - 5th 2025

2 - 5 września 2025 r.

Ryn, Poland

SECTIONS and PANELS

DISCUSSION PANEL

A vision for the transport of the future

Panel moderator – Prof. Jacyna Marianna, PhD, DSc

PANEL „10 years of the Transport Certification Center at the Faculty of Transport of the Warsaw University of Technology – experience and development”

Panel moderator – Andrzej Kochan, PhD, DSc, Assoc. Prof.

PANEL Rail-Mil Computers - ETCS

Panel moderator – Sławomir Jasiński, Ph.D.

PANEL „E-Laas Energy-optimal urban Logistics As A Service”

Panel moderator – Emilian Szczepański, PhD, DSc, Assoc. Prof.

PANEL BRIK II „Innovative technical solutions for the operation and management of railway infrastructure elements”

Panel moderator – Jacek Kukulski, PhD, DSc, Assoc. Prof.

SECTION 1 – INFRASTRUCTURE OF TRANSPORT AND COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING

Chairman – Prof. Krzysztof Zboiński, PhD, DSc

SECTION 2 – CONSTRUCTION AND EXPLOITATION OF TRANSPORT MEANS

Chairman – Jarosław Korzeb, PhD, DSc, Assoc. Prof.

SECTION 3 – LOGISTICS ENGINEERING AND TRANSPORT TECHNOLOGY

Chairman – Prof. Mariusz Izdebski, PhD, DSc

SECTION 4 – ORGANIZATION AND PLANNING OF TRANSPORT

Chairman – Prof. Mariusz Wasiak, PhD, DSc

SECTION 5 – TRANSPORT TELEMATICS AND INTELLIGENT TRANSPORT SYSTEMS

Chairman – Prof. Mirosław Siemieżyk, PhD, DSc

SECTION 6 – TRAFFIC CONTROL AND MANAGEMENT IN TRANSPORT

Chairman – Prof. Jacek Skorupski, PhD, DSc

SECTION 7 – CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE IN TRANSPORT

Chairman – Prof. Adam Rosiński, PhD, DSc

SECTION 8 – SAFETY ENGINEERING AND ECOLOGY IN TRANSPORT

Chairwoman – Prof. Iwona Grabarek, PhD, DSc

SECTION of YOUNG SCIENTISTS AND PHD STUDENTS

Chairman – Roland Jachimowski, PhD, DSc, Assoc. Prof.

General plan of the Conference Sessions

September 3rd Wednesday 2025					
	<u>King Wladyslaw Jagiello's Hall</u>	<u>Duke Witold's Hall</u>	<u>Duchess Anna's Hall</u>	<u>Grand Chapterhouse Hall</u>	<u>Chapterhouse Hall</u>
9.00 11.00	Opening Ceremony Plenary Session				
11.15 12.15	Plenary discussion panel				
12.45 13.45	Panel 10 years of the Transport Certification Center	Section 4 Session I	Section 6 Session I	Section 5 Session I	Section 7 Session I
15.30 17.00	Panel Rail-Mil Computers - ETCS	Section 4 Session II	Section 6 Session II	TC PAoFS	Section 8 Session I
17.15 18.30	Panel BRIK II	Section 4 Session III	Section 6 Session III	Section 3 Session I	Section 8 Session II
September 4th Thursday 2025					
	<u>King Wladyslaw Jagiello's Hall</u>	<u>Duke Witold's Hall</u>	<u>Duchess Anna's Hall</u>	<u>Grand Chapterhouse Hall</u>	<u>Chapterhouse Hall</u>
15.30 17.00	Section 2 Session I	Section 4 Session IV	Section 6 Session IV	Section 3 Session II	Section MNiD Session I
17.15 18.30	Section 2 Session II	Section 4 Session V	Section 6 Session V	Section 3 Session III	Section MNiD Session II
September 5th Friday 2025					
	<u>King Wladyslaw Jagiello's Hall</u>	<u>Duke Witold's Hall</u>	<u>Duchess Anna's Hall</u>	<u>Grand Chapterhouse Hall</u>	<u>Chapterhouse Hall</u>
8.30 10.00	Panel E-Laas	Section 2 Session III	Section 6 Session VI	Section 1 Session I	Section 8 Session III
10.15 11.30	Plenary Session Closing of the Conference				

Thematic PANEL / Panel Tematyczny

E-Laas Energy-Optimal Urban Logistics as a Service E-Laas Energetycznie optymalna logistyka miejska jako usługa

[King Wladyslaw Jagiello's Hall / Sala Króla Władysława Jagiełło](#)

Session II / Sesja II – Chairman / Przewodniczący – Emilian Szczepański

September 5th Friday in hours 8.30-10.00
5 września 2025 r. (piątek) godz. 8.30-10.00

panel w jęz. angielskim / panel in English

Ze Zhou, Fangting Zhou, Balázs Adam Kulcsár

Last-mile delivery problem with flexible time and location options under stochastic customer behaviour

Problem dostaw ostatniej mili z elastycznymi opcjami czasu i miejsca w warunkach stochastycznego zachowania klientów

Jakub Murawski, Piotr Franke

Sustainable logistics in polish cities – an overview of transport policies

Zrównoważona logistyka w polskich miastach – przegląd polityk transportowych

Konrad Lewczuk, Michał Kłodawski

Multi-domain microsimulation for evaluating energy efficiency in last-mile distribution

Wieloobszarowa mikrosymulacja do badania efektywności energetycznej systemów dystrybucyjnych ostatniej mili

Emilian Szczepański, Jan Paszkowski

Macroscopic simulation-based assessment of energy consumption and pollutant emissions in an urban logistics system

Makrosymulacyjna ocena zużycia energii i emisji zanieczyszczeń w miejskim systemie logistycznym

Plenary Session / Sesja plenarna

Jagiellonów 3 in 1 Hall / Sala Jagiellonów 3 w 1

September 5th (Friday) in hours 10.15-11.30

5 września 2025 r.(piątek) godz. 10.15-11.30

Chairwoman / Przewodnicząca – Marianna Jacyna

10.15 - 10.35 – Andrzej Szarata

The potential of advanced data to enhance transport planning in urban areas

Czy zaawansowane dane mogą poprawić proces planowania transportu w obszarach zurbanizowanych?

10.35 - 10.55 – Dariusz Kowalski

Medium- and long-term HR perspectives in the transport sector

Perspektywy kadrowe w transporcie w ujęciu średnio- i długookresowym

10.55 - 11.15 – Michał Klodawski, Konrad Lewczuk

Analysis of energy consumption in the last-mile delivery process based on simulation studies

Analiza symulacyjna energochłonności dostaw ostatniej mili

11.15 - 11.30

Closing of the Conference - Prof. Jacyna Marianna, PhD, DSc

Dean of the Faculty of Transport, Warsaw University of Technology

**Zamknięcie konferencji – prof. dr hab. inż. Marianna Jacyna
Dziekan Wydziału Transportu Politechniki Warszawskiej**